

Supplementary Material

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1 Rhythm (tapping) sub-battery

Overview

This section describes the computational methods used to extract sensorimotor synchronization features from finger-tapping data. The analysis pipeline processes tapping data collected during rhythmic stimuli (musical excerpts or metronome sequences) and self-paced (silence) conditions.

1.1 Data Preprocessing

1.1.1 Tempo-Based Segmentation

For stimuli containing tempo changes, tapping data is segmented into distinct windows based on the timing of tempo transitions. Given a set of taps $T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n\}$ and tempo change points $C = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m\}$, the data is partitioned into $m + 1$ windows:

$$W_1 = \{t \in T : t \leq c_1\} \quad (1)$$

$$W_i = \{t \in T : c_{i-1} < t \leq c_i\} \quad \text{for } i = 2, \dots, m \quad (2)$$

$$W_{m+1} = \{t \in T : t > c_m\} \quad (3)$$

1.1.2 Removal of Initial Taps

To account for entrainment effects at the beginning of each segment, the first n beats (default: $n = 3$) are excluded from analysis. Specifically, all taps occurring at or before the timestamp of the n -th beat are removed:

$$T_{\text{filtered}} = \{t \in T : t > \text{beatTime}_n\} \quad (4)$$

1.2 Feature Calculations

1.2.1 Inter-Tap Interval (ITI)

The inter-tap interval represents the typical time interval ([milliseconds](#)) between consecutive taps, computed as the median of successive tap differences.

Definition: Given a sequence of tap times $T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n\}$, the inter-tap intervals are:

$$\Delta t_i = t_{i+1} - t_i \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, \dots, n - 1 \quad (5)$$

The ITI is then:

$$\text{ITI} = \text{median}(\Delta t_1, \Delta t_2, \dots, \Delta t_{n-1}) \quad (6)$$

Units: milliseconds (ms)

1.2.2 Outlier Removal

Inter-tap intervals (ITIs) are filtered using the Interquartile Range (IQR) method before computing certain metrics. Given a dataset X :

$$Q_1 = P_{25}(X), \quad Q_3 = P_{75}(X) \quad (7)$$

$$\text{IQR} = Q_3 - Q_1 \quad (8)$$

$$X_{\text{filtered}} = \{x \in X : Q_1 - 1.5 \cdot \text{IQR} \leq x \leq Q_3 + 1.5 \cdot \text{IQR}\} \quad (9)$$

1.2.3 Variability

Variability quantifies the consistency of tapping performance, normalized by the participant's tapping rate. This measure captures the spread of inter-tap intervals relative to the central tendency.

Definition: After outlier removal from the inter-tap intervals ΔT :

$$\text{Variability} = \frac{P_{90}(\Delta T) - P_{10}(\Delta T)}{\text{median}(\Delta T)} \quad (10)$$

where P_{10} and P_{90} denote the 10th and 90th percentiles, respectively.

Interpretation: Lower values indicate more consistent tapping; higher values indicate greater variability. The normalization by median ITI allows comparison across different tempi.

Units: dimensionless ratio

1.2.4 Drift

Drift measures the systematic change in tapping tempo over the course of a trial. It is computed as the slope of a linear regression of inter-tap intervals against their ordinal position.

Definition: Given inter-tap intervals $\Delta t_1, \Delta t_2, \dots, \Delta t_{n-1}$ and their indices $i = 1, 2, \dots, n - 1$, a linear model is fitted:

$$\Delta t_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot i + \epsilon_i \quad (11)$$

The drift coefficient is:

$$\text{Drift} = \beta_1 \quad (12)$$

Interpretation:

- $\beta_1 > 0$: Participant is slowing down (increasing ITI over time)
- $\beta_1 < 0$: Participant is speeding up (decreasing ITI over time)
- $\beta_1 \approx 0$: Stable tempo maintenance

Units: ms/tap

1.2.5 Kuramoto Order Parameter and Phase

The Kuramoto model is used to assess the synchronization between the participant’s tapping and the stimulus beat structure, adapted for circular/phase-based analysis.

1.2.6 Metric Level Determination

Before computing the Kuramoto metrics, the participant’s performed tempo is matched to the closest metric level (half, original, or double the stimulus tempo).

Given the stimulus tempo BPM_{stim} , the possible metric levels are:

$$\text{BPM}_{\text{candidates}} = \left\{ \frac{\text{BPM}_{\text{stim}}}{2}, \text{BPM}_{\text{stim}}, 2 \cdot \text{BPM}_{\text{stim}} \right\} \quad (13)$$

The participant’s performed tempo is computed from their median ITI:

$$\text{BPM}_{\text{performed}} = \frac{60000}{\text{ITI}} \quad (14)$$

The closest metric level is selected by minimizing the absolute difference:

$$\text{BPM}_{\text{matched}} = \underset{\text{BPM} \in \text{BPM}_{\text{candidates}}}{\text{arg min}} \quad |\text{BPM} - \text{BPM}_{\text{performed}}| \quad (15)$$

1.2.7 Confidence Metric

The confidence in the metric level assignment is computed based on the relative distance to the closest and second-closest candidates:

$$\text{Confidence} = 1 - \frac{d_1}{d_2} \quad (16)$$

where d_1 and d_2 are the distances to the closest and second-closest metric levels, respectively.

Interpretation:

- Values close to 1 indicate high confidence (performed tempo is clearly closest to one metric level)
- Values close to 0 indicate low confidence (performed tempo is ambiguous between metric levels)

1.2.8 Order Parameter Amplitude (Synchronization Strength)

The [complex Kuramoto order parameter](#) quantifies the overall synchronization between taps and the reference beat period.

Definition: Given tap times $T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_N\}$ and the inter-beat interval $IBI = 6000/\text{BPM}_{\text{matched}}$ (in milliseconds), the **complex Kuramoto order parameter** is:

$$R = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N e^{i \cdot 2\pi \cdot t_k / IBI} \quad (17)$$

The **order parameter amplitude (synchronization strength)** is:

$$r = |R| \quad (18)$$

Interpretation:

- $r = 1$: Perfect synchronization (all taps occur at the same phase relative to the beat)
- $r = 0$: No synchronization (taps are uniformly distributed across phases)
- Typical values: $0.7 < r < 1$ indicates good synchronization

Units: dimensionless, range $[0, 1]$

1.2.9 Phase Angle (Asynchrony)

The mean phase angle indicates the average temporal relationship between taps and beats.

Definition:

$$\phi = \arg(R) \quad (19)$$

Interpretation:

- $\phi = 0$: Taps occur precisely on the beat
- $\phi > 0$: Taps tend to lag behind the beat
- $\phi < 0$: Taps tend to anticipate the beat (typical in human synchronization)

Units: radians, range $[-\pi, \pi]$

1.3 Special Handling for Self-Paced Conditions

For self-paced (silence) conditions where no external stimulus is present:

- **ITI, Variability, and Drift** are computed directly from the tap sequence without segmentation
- **Kuramoto metrics** (order parameter, phase angle) are not computed (set to NaN)
- **Metric level identification** is not applicable (set to NaN)

1.4 Output Variables

2 Movement sub-battery

2.1 Overview

This section describes the computational methods used to extract motor synchronization and movement features from accelerometer data. The analysis pipeline processes 3-axis accelerometer data collected during rhythmic stimuli (musical excerpts or metronome sequences) and self-paced (silence) conditions.

Variable	Description	Units
itic	Median inter-tap interval	ms
varc	Normalized variability	dimensionless
driftc	Tempo drift coefficient	ms/tap
ordc	Kuramoto order parameter	dimensionless [0,1]
angc	Kuramoto phase angle	radians
metric_levelc	Identified metric level	categorical (half/original/double)
bpmc	BPM at matched metric level	beats per minute
confidencec	Confidence in metric level assignment	dimensionless [0,1]

Table 1: Output variables from tap feature extraction.

2.2 Data Preprocessing

2.2.1 Upsampling

Accelerometer data is resampled to a uniform sampling rate of 100 Hz using linear interpolation, since raw accelerometer data from mobile devices is often irregularly sampled.

Definition: Given raw accelerometer samples at times t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n with 3D samples of accelerometer data $\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_n$ (where each $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$ for the three axes), a uniform time grid is created:

$$t_{\text{uniform}} = t_1, t_1 + \Delta t, t_1 + 2\Delta t, \dots, t_n \quad (20)$$

where $\Delta t = 10$ ms (corresponding to 100 Hz). Values are linearly interpolated onto this grid.

2.2.2 Tempo-Based Segmentation

For stimuli containing tempo changes, accelerometer data is segmented into distinct windows based on the timing of tempo transitions. Given accelerometer samples with timestamps $T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n\}$ and tempo change points $C = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m\}$, the data is partitioned into $m + 1$ windows:

$$W_1 = \{t \in T : t \leq c_1\} \quad (21)$$

$$W_i = \{t \in T : c_{i-1} < t \leq c_i\} \quad \text{for } i = 2, \dots, m \quad (22)$$

$$W_{m+1} = \{t \in T : t > c_m\} \quad (23)$$

2.2.3 Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

To reduce the three-dimensional accelerometer signal to a single representative time series, PCA is applied and the first principal component is extracted.

Definition: Given the accelerometer matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 3}$ (with columns for x, y, z axes), the covariance matrix is computed:

$$\mathbf{C} = \frac{1}{N-1} (\mathbf{A} - \bar{\mathbf{A}})^T (\mathbf{A} - \bar{\mathbf{A}}) \quad (24)$$

The eigenvectors $\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2, \mathbf{v}_3$ are computed and ordered by decreasing eigenvalue. The PC1 scores (the projection of the mean-centred data onto the first eigenvector) form a scalar time series:

$$\text{PC}_1 = (\mathbf{A} - \bar{\mathbf{A}}) \cdot \mathbf{v}_1 \quad (25)$$

Interpretation: The PC1 score vector $\text{PC}_1 = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_N\}$ captures the dominant axis of movement variability, providing a one-dimensional (scalar-valued) representation of the overall movement pattern at each time point.

2.3 Feature Calculations

2.3.1 Root Mean Square (RMS)

RMS quantifies the overall magnitude of movement activity.

Definition: Given the upsampled accelerometer matrix with samples $(x_i, y_i, z_i) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ for $i = 1, \dots, N$, the RMS is computed over the Euclidean norm of all three axes at each time point:

$$\text{RMS} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i^2 + y_i^2 + z_i^2)} \quad (26)$$

Interpretation: Higher RMS values indicate greater movement intensity. This metric captures the overall energy of movement regardless of its temporal structure.

Units: acceleration units (m/s² or g, depending on device calibration)

2.3.2 Tempo Estimation (Period Value)

The performed tempo is estimated by finding the period of maximum autocorrelation in the first principal component.

Definition: Given the first principal component score vector $\text{PC}_1 = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_N\}$, the autocorrelation function is computed:

$$R(\tau) = \sum_{i=1}^{N-\tau} p_i \cdot p_{i+\tau} \quad (27)$$

where τ is the lag in samples. To exclude unrealistically fast tempos (> 300 BPM), lags corresponding to periods less than 200 ms are skipped. The first significant peak in the autocorrelation is found:

$$\tau^* = \arg \max_{\tau > \tau_{\min}} R(\tau) \quad (28)$$

where $\tau_{\min} = \lceil 200 \cdot f_s / 1000 \rceil$ samples (20 samples at 100 Hz).

The estimated tempo is then:

$$\text{BPM} = \frac{60000}{\tau^* \cdot \Delta t} \quad (29)$$

where $\Delta t = 10$ ms is the sampling interval.

Units: beats per minute (BPM)

2.3.3 Periodicity Strength

Periodicity strength quantifies how rhythmically regular the movement pattern is.

Definition: Using the autocorrelation function $R(\tau)$ of the first principal component **score vector**, peaks at non-zero lags are identified. The periodicity strength is the ratio of the maximum non-zero-lag peak to the zero-lag autocorrelation:

$$\text{Periodicity Strength} = \frac{\max_{\tau>0} R(\tau)}{R(0)} \quad (30)$$

Interpretation:

- Values close to 1 indicate highly periodic, rhythmic movement
- Values close to 0 indicate aperiodic, irregular movement

Units: dimensionless ratio, range $[0, 1]$

2.3.4 Effective Dimensionality (ED)

Effective dimensionality measures the complexity of movement by quantifying how many independent dimensions are actively used.

Definition: Given the covariance matrix \mathbf{C} of the 3-axis accelerometer data, eigenvalues $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$ are computed. The normalized eigenvalues are:

$$\hat{\lambda}_j = \frac{\lambda_j}{\sum_{k=1}^3 \lambda_k} \quad (31)$$

The effective dimensionality is computed using the productory formula:

$$\text{ED} = \prod_{j=1}^3 \hat{\lambda}_j^{-\hat{\lambda}_j} \quad (32)$$

Interpretation:

- $\text{ED} \approx 1$: Movement is predominantly in one direction (linear)
- $\text{ED} \approx 2$: Movement spans a 2D plane
- $\text{ED} \approx 3$: Movement is distributed across all three spatial dimensions

Units: dimensionless, range $[1, 3]$

2.3.5 Phase Consistency (Synchronization)

Phase consistency measures how consistently movement phases align with stimulus beat times, adapted for circular/phase-based analysis across multiple metric levels.

Bandpass Filtering The first principal component **score vector** is bandpass filtered around the stimulus tempo $f_0 = \text{BPM}/60$ Hz with $\pm 20\%$ bandwidth:

$$f_{\text{low}} = f_0 - 0.2 \cdot f_0, \quad f_{\text{high}} = f_0 + 0.2 \cdot f_0 \quad (33)$$

A 2nd-order Butterworth bandpass filter is applied.

Instantaneous Phase Extraction The Hilbert transform is applied to extract the instantaneous phase:

$$\tilde{z}(t) = \text{PC}_1^{\text{filtered}}(t) + i \cdot \mathcal{H}\{\text{PC}_1^{\text{filtered}}(t)\} \quad (34)$$

$$\phi(t) = \arg(\tilde{z}(t)) \quad (35)$$

Metric Level Computation Phase consistency is computed at three metric levels:

- **Half metric:** Beat times downsampled by factor of 2
- **Original metric:** Beat times as annotated
- **Double metric:** Beat times interpolated to double frequency

Phase Consistency Calculation For each metric level with beat times $B = \{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_M\}$, the phases at beat times are extracted: $\phi(b_1), \phi(b_2), \dots, \phi(b_M)$.

The phase consistency (analogous to the **order parameter amplitude**) is:

$$\text{Phase Consistency} = \left| \frac{1}{M} \sum_{k=1}^M e^{i \cdot \phi(b_k)} \right| \quad (36)$$

Interpretation:

- Values close to 1 indicate consistent phase relationship between movement and beats
- Values close to 0 indicate no consistent phase relationship

Units: dimensionless, range $[0, 1]$

2.3.6 Proportion of Synchronized Power

This metric quantifies what proportion of movement energy is concentrated around the beat frequency and its metric subdivisions.

Definition: The power spectrum of the first principal component **score vector** is computed via FFT:

$$P(f) = |\text{FFT}(\text{PC}_1)|^2 \quad (37)$$

For each metric level (half, original, double tempo), the proportion of power within $\pm 5\%$ of that tempo is computed:

$$\text{Prop}_{\text{level}} = \frac{\sum_{f \in [f_{\text{level}} \pm 5\%]} P(f)}{\sum_f P(f)} \quad (38)$$

Interpretation: Higher values indicate that more movement energy is concentrated at the beat-related frequency, suggesting better entrainment to the rhythm.

Units: dimensionless ratio, range [0, 1]

3 Tempo error

Tempo error measures how closely the performed movement tempo matches the stimulus tempo.

Definition: Given the performed tempo $\text{BPM}_{\text{performed}}$ and the stimulus tempo BPM_{stim} , the closest metric level is identified:

$$\text{BPM}_{\text{matched}} = \arg \min_{x \in \{\frac{\text{BPM}_{\text{stim}}}{2}, \text{BPM}_{\text{stim}}, 2 \cdot \text{BPM}_{\text{stim}}\}} |x - \text{BPM}_{\text{performed}}| \quad (39)$$

The tempo accuracy is the absolute difference:

$$\text{Tempo error} = \frac{|\text{BPM}_{\text{performed}} - \text{BPM}_{\text{matched}}|}{\text{BPM}_{\text{matched}}} \quad (40)$$

Interpretation: Lower values indicate better tempo matching. Values are averaged across all non-silence trials for each participant.

Units: beats per minute (BPM)

3.1 Special Handling for Self-Paced Conditions

For self-paced (silence) conditions where no external stimulus is present:

- **RMS, Tempo Estimation, Periodicity Strength, and Effective Dimensionality** are computed directly from the movement sequence without segmentation
- **Phase Consistency and Proportion of Synchronized Power** are not computed (set to NaN)
- **Metric level identification** is not applicable (set to NaN)

3.2 Output Variables

3.2.1 Raw Features (per segment)

Variable	Description	Units
rms	Root mean square of movement	acceleration units
periodVal	Estimated performed tempo	BPM
strength	Periodicity strength	dimensionless [0,1]
ed	Effective dimensionality	dimensionless [1,3]
phaseConsistency	Phase consistency (3 metric levels)	dimensionless [0,1]
proportion	Proportion synchronized power (3 metric levels)	dimensionless [0,1]

Table 2: Raw output variables from movement feature extraction (per segment).

Variable	Description	Units
tempo_accuracy	Mean absolute tempo error	BPM
avg_ed_freedance	Mean effective dimensionality (free dance)	dimensionless
avg_rms_freedance	Mean RMS (free dance)	acceleration units
avg_phase_sync	Mean phase consistency (best metric level)	dimensionless
avg_period_conf	Mean periodicity strength	dimensionless

Table 3: Aggregated output variables from movement feature extraction (per participant).

Figure 1: Estimating pitch and rhythmic accuracy of a singing recording. Reproduced with permission from Pitkaniemi et al. (2025).

3.2.2 Aggregated Features (per participant)

4 Singing

The analysis pipeline for a singing back task is illustrated in Figure 1,. It begins with the audio waveform of each recording (A), from which an audio envelope is estimated to remove leading and trailing silence (B). A geometric pitch template of the target song serves as the reference for comparison (C). The participant’s estimated pitch contour (blue) is first aligned with a pitch-shifted version of the template (red) (D), after which dynamic time warping (DTW) is applied to obtain an optimal temporal matching between the contours (E). Segment boundaries are then introduced at the note-change discontinuities of the template (F), enabling the computation of segment-level pitch deviations (G). Finally, the DTW warping path (H) is used to quantify rhythmic accuracy.

From these representations, several performance metrics are derived. Pitch error is computed as the amplitude-weighted mean absolute difference between the participant’s instantaneous pitch and the expected pitch, expressed in semitones. To account for gradual drifting away from the key, a detrended pitch error measure applies the same calculation after removing slow pitch trends. For segmentwise pitch error, the pitch contour is quantized by taking the median pitch within each template-defined segment, after which the same semitone-difference procedure is applied; a detrended segmentwise pitch error parallels this method using the detrended contour. Pitch direction error compares the Parsons-code-like directional patterns of successive segments between the participant and the template, summing the absolute differences in these ascent/descent descriptors. Relational pitch error extends this by focusing on the mag-

nitude of inter-segment pitch intervals rather than just direction. Finally, rhythm error reflects the amount of temporal warping needed for DTW to align the participant’s pitch contour with the metronomic template, normalized by the duration of the excerpt.

5 Emotion

Emotion measures consist of two separate tests, *Short Musical Affect Recognition Test* (SMART) and *Perception of Affect in Music* (PAM).

SMART is an adaptive musical emotion recognition ability test that uses naturalistic music stimuli and binary choices. It has good psychometric properties, and is suitable for a broad range of ability levels and delivers consistent results across various demographic variables. The output of the test is SMART Score ranging from -5 to +5 where population average is 1.4 (SD = 1.29). SMART is fully documented at https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/aub8n_v1.

PAM captures perceived core affect dimensions in music (valence, arousal, and intensity) using Likert-type scales. Normative data are available, allowing deviations from the norms to be estimated either by scale, target emotion category, or subcategory. Reliability, interface issues, and construct validity checks of the PAM are currently underway.